

A Generally Covariant Quantum Theory

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Abstract

We introduce a framework which permits to construct generally covariant spaces of quantum states as direct sums of representations. Our starting point is based on the historical works of Sachs and McCarthy on the BMS group. The local symmetry group is defined, its structure is investigated, some representations are constructed. Several aspects of the framework are revealed: the existence of Schrodinger equation; gravitons as quanta of tensor fields of rank ≥ 3 as well as of *infinite rank* (there is no field of rank 2); covariant translations replacing Poincaré translations; equation of motion in the case of uniform pure-rank tensor field. The framework needs further

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development and verification, and in the case turns out to be correct, provides higher-order gravity and accelerating-frame corrections to the physics of elementary particles in curved spacetime, as well as in other relevant domains, consistent with a hypothetical generally covariant quantum field theory.

1 Introduction

In 1962, Sachs, building upon the previous works of Bondi and Metzner on gravitational waves, introduced us to the BMS group (also called the GBM group by himself, the \mathcal{B} group by McCarthy) ([9]). The transformations of the BMS group are those which somewhat leave invariant the asymptotic behaviour at infinity of the metric. The usual translations seen in the familiar Poincaré group are replaced with a larger class of the supertranslations. Denote by N the group of super translations, we have ([9], Theorem IV.1) that N is a normal subgroup of BMS and that $\text{BMS}/N \cong O(3, 1)$.

The irreducible representations of the BMS group were later completely determined and classified by the comprehensive works of McCarthy *et al* ([4]-[7]). One particular interesting result is that one finds the discreteness of the spin values for positive mass (opposed to the case of Poincaré group's representations where there are also continuous spin values). Another is the non-trivial decomposition of BMS-irreducible representations into direct sums of Poincaré's group's irreducible representations. This might be interpreted as the interaction between gravitational field and matter fields, which creates particles. It is also speculated that such consideration might have influences on particle physics phenomena.

The asymptotically flat metrics come naturally with an omnipotent observer at ∞ , whose proper time is measured by the term dt in the metric. To an observer at finite distances from gravitational sources, there exists also a coordinate system corresponding to the locally inertial frame: the Fermi normal coordinates ([1]). It is thus natural to consider the group of transformations which leave the metric invariant to some orders with respect to the Fermi coordinates. The representations of such group might, speculatively, contain some non-trivial information of the influence of gravity on the physics of elementary particles.

The starting point of this article is thus, to repeat locally what Sachs and McCarthy have done asymptotically at infinity. The local group is constructed, their representations investigated. Some particular interesting results are: the existence of Schrodinger equation, in principle, depends on the representation; a ladder of corrections which include, in second order, the representations of Poincaré group, with covariant translations replacing instantaneous translations; nonperturbative representations which are not part of any finite-order correction; gravitons are described by, in contrast to the popular belief, necessarily rank 3 tensors; gravitons are radiated by moving objects.

We also establish, to each one of the successive finite orders, a tensor field in the presence of which an explicit equation of movement in the uniform, pure-order case is given. The framework seemingly can be generalized to the case of an accelerating observer.

2 The local symmetry group

Consider an observer Alice, noted A , falling along a geodesic of spacetime, fixing at a certain proper time. In her Fermi normal coordinates, the metric to second order takes the form ([8], (6.1)-(6.6), citing [1]):

$$\begin{aligned}
 g_{00} &= -1 - R_{0l0m}x^l x^m \\
 g_{0i} &= g^{0i} = -\frac{2}{3}R_{0lim}x^l x^m \\
 g_{ij} &= \delta_{ij} - \frac{1}{3}R_{iljm}x^l x^m \\
 g^{00} &= -1 + R_{0l0m}x^l x^m \\
 g^{ij} &= \delta^{ij} + \frac{1}{3}R^i{}^j{}_{lm}x^l x^m \\
 g &= -1 + \frac{1}{3}(R_{lm} - 2R_{0l0m})x^l x^m
 \end{aligned}$$

where Latin indices go from 1 to 3. For convenience, we also write these equations as $g_{\mu\nu} = \eta_{\mu\nu} - R_{\mu l \nu m}^* x^l x^m$, where Greek indices go from 0 to 3, and $\eta_{\mu\nu}$ is the Minkowsky metric with sign convention $(-, +, +, +)$. It should be noted that, unlike $R_{\mu\rho\nu\lambda}$, R_{iljm}^* does not transform as a tensor.

Consider now a transformation:

$$\bar{x}^\mu = f^\mu(x^\nu)$$

where f^μ s are defined locally of class \mathcal{C}^2 (and thus we can always take the domain of definition of f^μ smaller if needed). The position and time of A is fixed to $(0, 0, 0, 0)$. f^μ has the following Tayler development around 0:

$$f^\mu(x^\nu) = \alpha^\mu + \beta_\nu^\mu x^\nu + \gamma_{\nu\lambda}^\mu x^\nu x^\lambda + O(|x|^3)$$

(γ is chosen to be symmetric with respect to lower indices). The norm $|x|$ is the topological Euclidean \mathbb{R}^4 norm, employed here for the study of locally asymptotic behaviour, not to be confused with the invariant ds^2 .

One should note that there exist non trivial transformations whose Taylor series are identically zero except at first order, e.g. the transformation $x^\mu \rightarrow x^\mu(1 + \exp(-(\frac{a^\mu}{x^\mu})^2))$.

To say that f^μ leaves the metric invariant to order $|x|^2$, we require that in the new coordinate system \bar{x}^μ , the metric to the second order is of the same above form, with the Riemann tensor's coefficients $R_{\mu l \nu m}$ replaced by the coefficients in the new coordinates $\bar{R}_{\mu l \nu m}$. The transformation matrices are $\Lambda_\nu^\mu = \frac{\partial f^\mu}{\partial x^\nu} = \beta_\nu^\mu$.

Direct calculations yield the following conditions on the coefficients α, β and γ :

$$\begin{aligned}(\Lambda^{-1})^\mu_\lambda (\Lambda^{-1})^\nu_\rho \eta_{\mu\nu} &= \eta_{\lambda\rho} + \bar{R}^*_{\lambda i \rho j} \alpha^i \alpha^j \\ \bar{R}^*_{\lambda l \rho m} (\beta^l_\mu \alpha^m + \alpha^l \beta^m_\mu) &= 0 \\ (\Lambda^{-1})^\mu_\lambda (\Lambda^{-1})^\nu_\rho R^*_{\mu l \nu m} &= \bar{R}^*_{\lambda i \rho j} (\gamma^i_{lm} \alpha^j + \alpha^i \gamma^j_{lm} + \beta^i_l \beta^j_m) \\ \bar{R}^*_{\lambda i \rho j} (\gamma^i_{0\mu} \alpha^j + \alpha^i \gamma^j_{0\mu} + \beta^i_0 \beta^j_\mu) &= 0\end{aligned}$$

Proposition 2.1. *The local transformations of class \mathcal{C}^2 (twice continuously differentiable) satisfying the above conditions and for which $\det(\beta^i_\nu) \neq 0$ and $\alpha^\mu = 0$ form a group.*

Proof. If f and g leave the expression to second order invariant, so is the composed $f \circ g$.

The identity of the group is taken to be the identical $f^\mu(x^\nu) = x^\mu$.

The inverse element exists by the inverse function theorem. That it is contained in the group is obvious. \square

And thus from now on the above-defined group will be denoted G_A , where A takes into account Alice's reference frame and the proper time of consideration.

In flat space time, we have that $R_{\mu\rho\nu\lambda} = 0$, $\bar{R}_{\mu\rho\nu\lambda} = 0$ and $R^*_{\mu l \nu m} = 0$, $\bar{R}^*_{\mu l \nu m} = 0$. The conditions for α, β, γ become simply $(\Lambda^{-1})^\mu_\lambda (\Lambda^{-1})^\nu_\rho \eta_{\mu\nu} = \eta_{\lambda\rho}$, and thus $G_A = \{x^\mu \rightarrow \Lambda^\mu_\nu x^\nu + O(|x|^2), \Lambda \in O(3, 1)\}$.

In general, we are required that $\Lambda \in O(3, 1)$ and satisfies $R^*_{\mu l \nu m} = \Lambda^\lambda_\mu \Lambda^\rho_\nu \Lambda^i_l \Lambda^j_m \bar{R}^*_{\lambda i \rho j}$ and $\Lambda^i_0 \Lambda^j_\mu \bar{R}^*_{\lambda i \rho j} = 0$, which, explicitly, are complicated constraints on Λ given in term of $R_{\mu l \nu m}$.

And thus, in general, $G_A = \{x^\mu \rightarrow \beta^\mu_\nu x^\nu + O(|x|^2), \beta \in O_A(3, 1)\}$, where $O_A(3, 1)$ is a subgroup of $O(3, 1)$ determined by the conditions above.

The above argument shows that the group $O_A(3, 1)$ is at most $O(3, 1)$. Now to each point A in spacetime, to each free-falling observer through A and to each space orientation of the free-falling observer, there exists an associated Fermi normal coordinate. These Fermi normal coordinates are related to each other at first order by the Lorentz transformations. And thus the group $O_A(3, 1)$ is at least $O(3, 1)$.

Conclusion: $O_A(3, 1) \cong O(3, 1)$.

3 The structure of G_A

Proposition 3.1. *Let $N = \{Id + O(|x|^2)\}$. We have that N is a normal subgroup of G_A and $G_A/N \cong O_A(3, 1)$.*

Proof. Let $g \in O_A(3, 1)$ and $f \in N$. In order to prove that $N \triangleleft G_A$, it suffices to show that $g \circ f \circ g^{-1} = Id + O(|x|^2)$, which is obvious. \square

Remark. Contrary to the case of the BMS group, here N is not abelian. The author cannot help but notice that the existence of an abelian normal subgroup is quite important to apply Mackey's method to induce representations ([4]), and Sachs's arguments and constructions do seem to favour the cause. And thus, we would want to impose some conditions on N such that it becomes an abelian normal subgroup of G_A . However, we didn't succeed in doing so.

Although N is not abelian, $O(3, 1)$ acts on N via the above action, and thus we have a semi-direct product $G_A = N \rtimes O(3, 1)$. If one is not able to find a counterpart of the abelian normal subgroup of supertranslations of the BMS group, one is forced to work in the non-abelian setting. There is a general framework for this case ([3]), but the theory is quite complicated to the author. There's also a need to define exactly what we mean by *taking the domain of definition smaller if needed*, and a proper topology for N ; in view of [3], what we would need might be a Borel structure ([2]) instead of a topology structure. All that is necessary if we want to classify G_A 's irreducible representations, but that is not the purpose of this article.

3.1 Constructing representations

Besides attacking the problem of classifying irreducible representations of G_A , we can also collect some by lifting known representations of $O(3, 1)$ and inducing those of N . The unitary representations of $O(3, 1)$ is well known ([10]), and corresponds to our present knowledge of Lorentz invariant particle physics. The unitary representations of N is however not as known, and corresponds, speculatively, to gravity as well as generally-moving-frame corrections.

Let $\rho : G_A \rightarrow GL(V)$ be a representation of G_A . ρ is also a representation of $O(3, 1)$ as $\rho(\Lambda)$ acts on V . Thus V is decomposed into irreducible representations of $O(3, 1)$ corresponding to different kinds of quantum states.

We'll now focus on the case of elementary particles. Some familiar kinds of elementary particles are:

- Spin 0 scalar particles (Higg bosons). The corresponding 1-dimensional unitary irreducible representation of $O(3, 1)$ is $\rho(\Lambda)(\phi) = \phi$, that is, $O(3, 1)$ acts trivially.
- Spin 1 vector particles (photon, weak bosons, strong gluons). The corresponding 4-dimensional irreducible representation of $O(3, 1)$ is $\rho(\Lambda)(a^\mu) = \Lambda^\mu_\nu a^\nu$.
- Spin $\frac{1}{2}$ spinor particles (electron, leptons).

It should be helpful to construct an example for the case of spin 0 scalar particles.

In order to obtain a space large enough for a faithful representation of N , we take $\oplus_{x^\mu \in \mathbb{R}^4} \mathbb{C}_x = \{\phi : \mathbb{R}^4 \rightarrow \mathbb{C}\}$ with some conditions of regularity. Now $O(3, 1)$ acts on this space trivially, and we let N act on this space by $\circ f^{-1}$ inside the argument (in fact, this is the only nontrivial representation of N that we know). And thus:

$$\rho(\Lambda)\phi = \phi$$

$$\begin{aligned}\rho(\Lambda \circ f)\phi &= \phi \circ f^{-1} \\ \rho(f \circ \Lambda)\phi &= \phi \circ f^{-1}\end{aligned}$$

Note that the coordinates here are fixed coordinates of the observer A . If we want the index we use for ϕ corresponds to the coordinates after the transformation, we have $\rho(\Lambda)\phi = \phi \circ \Lambda^{-1}$, $\rho(\Lambda \circ f)\phi = \phi \circ f^{-1} \circ \Lambda^{-1}$, $\rho(f \circ \Lambda)\phi = \phi \circ \Lambda^{-1} \circ f^{-1}$. This double multiplication is interpreted as follows: one accounts for the effect of motions on the physics, the other is simply a rearrangement of indices. We obtain the space of 1-particle wave function, which is the smallest generally covariant spin 0 representation.

Remark. The action of f by indices only serves as an example. It's, *a priori*, highly unlikely that the physical effect of higher order movements would be described by the action of index exchange. Λ itself can also act by exchanging indices, and this action commute with the external action. We'll see later on that, in order for the Schrodinger equation to exist for all observers, if N acts by exchanging indices, Λ must also act by exchanging indices.

Many-particle representations can be constructed from 1-particle representation. Let ρ_0 be the representation in which N acts trivially, and ρ_i be the representation in which N exchanges the indices. Since these are the only representations of N that we know by now, a 2 particle system can be $\rho_0 \oplus \rho_0$, $\rho_i \oplus \rho_0$, $\rho_i \oplus \rho_i$ or an unknown irreducible 2 particle representation. We speculate that the scattering processes, such as $e^+e^- \rightarrow 2\gamma$, should be assigned to a quantum state in the direct sum of 2 spin $\frac{1}{2}$ particles and 2 spin 1 particles.

4 Schrodinger equation

Now consider a generally covariant quantum system observed by Alice. Since the system is generally covariant, it should be described by a unitary representation (ρ, V) of the group G_A .

Suppose Alice constructs a Hamiltonian H_A (which is a self-adjoint operator acting over V , with some continuous and regular conditions with respect to the action of N , typically contains operators of the form $a^\dagger a$, where a decreases the number of particles and a^\dagger increases the number of particles) and verifies that, in her reference frame, the system evolves according to the Schrodinger equation:

$$i\hbar\partial_{t_A}v_A = H_A v_A$$

Another observer named Bob, noted B , with coordinates $x_B^\mu = f(x_A^\mu)$ would observe the state vector $\rho(f)v_A$, and thus his Schrodinger equation:

$$i\hbar\partial_{t_A}\rho(f)^{-1}v_B = H_A\rho(f)^{-1}v_B$$

If N acts trivially on the set of indices ($\rho = \rho_0$), we find:

$$H_B = (\Lambda_0^0)^{-1}(\rho(f)H_A\rho(f)^{-1} - i\hbar c\Lambda_0^i\partial_i)$$

If N acts by exchanging indices ($\rho = \rho_i$), since the operator $\rho(f)^{-1}$ exchanges the indices in \mathbb{R}^4 , it does not commute with the partial derivative. Let $f = g \circ \Lambda$, $\rho(f)^{-1} = \rho(\Lambda)^{-1}\rho(g)^{-1}$. Let $T = \rho(g)^{-1}$ which only exchanges the indices without influencing the values of a section. We have:

$$\begin{aligned}\partial_{t_A}(T(v))(x_B^\mu) &= \partial_{t_A}(v(g(x_A^\mu))) \\ &= \partial_\mu v(g(x_A^\mu)) \frac{\partial g^\mu}{\partial x^\nu} \partial_{t_A} x^\nu\end{aligned}$$

Here we're blocked with the term $g(x_A^\mu)$. We'll try again with $f = \Lambda \circ g$, $\rho(f)^{-1} = \rho(g)^{-1}\rho(\Lambda)^{-1}$. We have:

$$\begin{aligned}\partial_{t_A}(T(v))(x_B^\mu) &= \partial_{t_A}(v(g(x_A^\mu))) \\ &= \partial_\mu v(g(x_A^\mu)) \frac{\partial g^\mu}{\partial x^\nu} \partial_{t_A} x^\nu \\ &= (T\partial_\mu v)(\Lambda^{-1}x_B^\mu)(\Lambda_g)_0^\mu \Lambda_0^0\end{aligned}$$

There doesn't seem to be a good way to obtain a Schrodinger equation for observer B in this case.

What if we let N acts by exchanging indices, and Λ by both the external action and the index exchange? (To facilitate a curious reader, we can denote the external action by $\rho(f)$, and the index exchange action by T_f , in order to make the calculation tractable; T_f and $\rho(f)$ commute). The result is that:

$$H_B = (\Lambda_0^0)^{-2}(\rho(f)H_A\rho(f)^{-1} - i\hbar c\Lambda_0^0\Lambda_0^i\partial_i)$$

(The difference with the case of trivial action of N is only two Λ_0^0 terms, which is quite small)

Thus, the existence and the form of a Hamiltonian for the Schrodinger equation is quite sensitive to the G_A -representation. We see that in our examples, the Schrodinger equation doesn't exist for all observers if N acts by exchanging indices and $O(3,1)$ doesn't; Schrodinger equation exists when N acts trivially or both N and $O(3,1)$ acts by exchanging indices (which commute with the external action of $O(3,1)$).

Again, the highly unrealistic index representation serves to demonstrate that, in general, in the framework, Schrodinger equation is not guaranteed to exist. It might be that some representations are not used to describe real phenomena; it might also be that there are systems not evolving according to any Schrodinger equation; it might be both.

5 Successive corrections

Let $N_k = \{Id + O(|x|^k)\}$ for $k \geq 2$ and $N_\infty = \bigcap_{k=2}^\infty N_k$ (recall the transformation $x^\mu(1 + \exp(-\frac{a^\mu}{x^\mu})^2)$), we see that $N_\infty \neq \{Id\}$.

It's easy to see that $N_k/N_{k+1} \cong \mathbb{R}^{4^{k+1}}$. The action of $\mathbb{R}^{4^{k+1}}$ on N_{k+1} is given by:

$$(\gamma_{\mu_1\mu_2\dots\mu_k}^\mu, f) \rightarrow (x^\mu + \gamma_{\mu_1\mu_2\dots\mu_k}^\mu x^{\mu_1} x^{\mu_2} \dots x^{\mu_k}) \circ f \circ (x^\mu + \gamma_{\mu_1\mu_2\dots\mu_k}^\mu x^{\mu_1} x^{\mu_2} \dots x^{\mu_k})^{-1}$$

These newly discovered successive corrections imply the possibility that invariants similar to $ds^2 = \eta_{\mu\nu} dx^\mu dx^\nu$ might exist at higher orders, restricting permitted representations. This is, of course, to be confirmed by experiments.

It may be worth noting that the form of this action does suggest the presence of a closed string-like/loop-like structure.

5.1 N_2 -correction

Suppose we want to find representations of G_A in which N_3 acts trivially, that is, representations of $N_2/N_3 \rtimes O(3, 1)$, where $O(3, 1)$ acts on $N_2/N_3 \cong \mathbb{R}^{64}$ by $(\Lambda\gamma)_{\nu\lambda}^\mu = \Lambda_\sigma^\mu (\Lambda^{-1})_\nu^\sigma (\Lambda^{-1})_\lambda^\epsilon \gamma_{\delta\epsilon}^\sigma$.

Suppose further that $\gamma_{\nu\lambda}^\mu$ acts on \mathbb{R}^4 by $x^\mu \rightarrow x^\mu + \gamma_{\nu\lambda}^\mu \eta^{\nu\lambda}$. Then we retrieve the action of $O(3, 1)$ on \mathbb{R}^4 in the Poincaré group, and thus we also obtain the representations of the Poincaré group.

Remark. The ordinary translations $x^\mu \rightarrow x^\mu + a^\mu$, in the above representation, is replaced with the covariant transformation $x^\mu \rightarrow x^\mu + \gamma_{\nu\lambda}^\mu x^\nu x^\lambda$ for which $\gamma_{\nu\lambda}^\mu \eta^{\nu\lambda} = -\gamma_{00}^\mu + \gamma_{11}^\mu + \gamma_{22}^\mu + \gamma_{33}^\mu = a^\mu$. In the limit $c \rightarrow \infty$, $\gamma_{00}(x^0)^2$ becomes the dominant term, and $x^\mu \rightarrow x^\mu + \gamma_{00}^\mu c^2 t^2 = x^\mu - a^\mu c^2 t^2$. The square c^2 also explains why it might be so hard to detect the effect of such covariant translations.

Thus, if the present text is consistent with the fundamental laws of nature, it's no longer possible to move in one direction in spacetime without somehow affecting the other direction(s). We, under Einstein's giant shadow, have replaced the instantaneous "spooky" translations of the Poincaré group by second-order covariant translations. There are many covariant translations corresponding to one Poincaré group's translation.

There's still a canonical choice of $\gamma_{00}^\mu \neq 0$ and all the other terms = 0 which would permit a global construction from local charts.

5.2 N_∞ -correction

Since the representations of N_∞ avoids perturbative series to all orders, they are the *instantons* that are only found as exact nonperturbative solutions. Further down the line, we're going to construct successive tensor representations of G_A , which corresponds to tensorial fields of gravitons. The remaining group, N_∞ , is intriguingly non tensorial and non trivial, and quite large even. The only representations of N_∞ that we know (which are somehow regular/continuous) are the trivial representation and the index representation.

5.3 Gravitons

Gravitons, as quanta of gravity field, thus, if exist, are very rich in nature. They can be in any of the successive higher-order N_k groups, or a gravi-instanton of N_∞ , or any mixing of these; in short, any representation of the general symmetry group.

At second order, we already see that γ is acted upon by $O(3, 1)$ as a tensor of rank 3. This might partly explain the current difficulty when dealing with gravitons: there is no particle associated with a rank 2 tensor. The approximate rank 2 tensor $h_{\mu\nu} = g_{\mu\nu} - \eta_{\mu\nu}$ can be derived from our rank 3 tensor by factoring out the approximate translations, leaving a subspace of dimension 16. In any case, $h_{\mu\nu}$ should stay an adequate weak field approximation.

The description of a 2nd order free graviton is then quite straightforward. At each point in spacetime, it is described by a tensor of rank 3: $g_{\nu\lambda}^\mu$. The wavefunction is $g_{\nu\lambda}^\mu(x)$.

Under $Id + \Lambda$, g transforms as a rank 3 tensor. Under $Id + \gamma$, g transforms additively: $\rho(Id + \gamma_{\nu\lambda}^\mu)g = g_{\nu\lambda}^\mu + \gamma_{\nu\lambda}^\mu$ (in fact, to each matrix M of size 64×64 , there associates an action of N_2/N_3 on \mathbb{R}^{64} given by $(\gamma, g) \rightarrow g + M\gamma$. Here we're only considering the action with $M = Id$). Under a general 2nd order transformation $Id + \Lambda + \gamma$, there needs to be a bit more effort to work out the transformation of g , since $Id + \Lambda + \gamma$ doesn't factor as a product of $Id + \Lambda$ and $Id + \gamma$. This is due to the fact that the group extension $N_2/N_3 \rightarrow G_A/N_3 \rightarrow O(3, 1)$ is not a direct product.

The transformation of g under $Id + \gamma$ tells us that gravitons appear where there is acceleration, or equivalently gravity.

A treatment on Schrodinger equation reveals that there might exist a Schrodinger equation for gravitons. This is, of course, to be verified by further developments and experiments.

6 Gravitons and movement

Suppose now that we've developed a correct quantum gravity by this framework, so that gravitons are described by a representation ρ . Let Charlie be carrying an object, moving with respect to Alice's reference frame such that Charlie's Fermi normal coordinates are related to Alice's by:

$$x_C^\mu = f^\mu(x_A^\nu)$$

(Charlie's equation of motion in Alice's reference frame is $f^i(x_A^\nu) = 0$). The movement is general.

Now suppose in Charlie's reference frame, the object doesn't create any graviton, or we can say that we restrict ourselves to the gravitons created by the effect of moving. Thus these gravitons are at vacuum level, $|0\rangle$. Now since our theory is covariant, we can calculate the gravitons' level in Alice's reference. Since we have $x_A^\mu = (f^{-1})(x_C^\mu)$, we obtain $|g\rangle_A = \rho(f^{-1})|0\rangle$.

And thus an object moving with equation of motion $f^i(x^\mu) = 0$ would radiate gravitons to the state $|g\rangle_A = \rho(f^{-1})|0\rangle$, where f^i and f^0 are chosen such that f^μ becomes a

system of Fermi normal coordinates.

Now these gravitons should influence the movements of the surrounding test masses in such a way that in the classical limit, we retrieve the metric tensor $g_{\mu\nu}$ and the geodesic equation.

6.1 Graviton fields

Since we are now prepared with the many abelian groups $N_2/N_3, N_3/N_4, \dots$, we can assume the existence of corresponding tensorial graviton fields $G_{\mu_1\mu_2}^\mu(x), G_{\mu_1\mu_2\mu_3}^\mu(x), \dots$. The k th order field is described by a tensor of rank $k + 1$.

It would be a good practice to find the equation of motion for an object in the presence of a tensor field. This is quite straightforward for the uniform case: consider a static observer A with static matter, and consider observer B moving with respect to A by the equation $f^i(x_A) = x_B^i = 0$ (with f^μ in our symmetry group).

In Alice's reference frame, there is no tensor fields, and thus $G_A = 0$, and there is no movement. In Bob's reference frame, since $x_B^\mu = (f^{-1})(x_A^\mu)$, we have that $G_B = \rho(f^{-1})G_A$.

(As discussed above, we have many available actions of N_k/N_{k+1} on $\mathbb{R}^{4^{k+1}}$. Let's give a try to the simplest action, $(\gamma, g) \rightarrow g + \gamma$).

And thus if f is such that $f^{-1}(x^\mu) = x^\mu + \gamma_{\mu_1\mu_2\dots\mu_k}^\mu x^{\mu_1}x^{\mu_2}\dots x^{\mu_k}$, the gravity field in Bob's reference frame would be the pure $(k + 1)$ th order graviton field $G = \gamma$.

And by the above discussion, we obtain the local equation of motion for an object in the presence of a uniform purely rank $k + 1$ gravity field G :

$$(x^i + G_{\mu_1\mu_2\dots\mu_k}^i x^{\mu_1}x^{\mu_2}\dots x^{\mu_k})^{-1} = 0$$

In the completely covariant picture, there need to be, in addition to the tensor fields, coupled fields as well as N_∞ fields. We speculate that in order to retrieve the metric tensor $g_{\mu\nu}$, the Ricci tensor $R_{\mu\nu}$ and the Riemann tensor $R_{\mu\nu\lambda\sigma}$, it is impossible to overlook the coupled fields and the N_∞ fields. And consequently, they should also be necessary for the retrieval of the geodesic equation as well as Einstein's field equation, which will be completed elsewhere. Nevertheless, it might also be possible that gravity is described by a representation in which the action is trivial for N_∞ , or even truncated at finite order.

(Here we use the terminology *coupled fields* to describe the fact that, the additive action of N_k/N_{k+1} on $\mathbb{R}^{4^{k+1}}$, when extended to a full action of the general symmetry group, becomes quite complicated with the actions of the lower order groups all involved).

7 An *ansatz* for the non inertial frames

All our considerations by now are restricted to free falling observers, which correspond to inertial frames. For non inertial frames, the Fermi normal coordinates don't exist in general, but there is a system of Fermi coordinates in which the metric tensor is of the form:

$$g = \begin{bmatrix} -1 - 2a_\mu x^\mu & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 1 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 1 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 1 \end{bmatrix} + O(|x|^2)$$

We make the *ansatz* that all the arguments in the previous sections still valid in this case, and thus we can construct generally covariant quantum states for David who is standing at $(0, 0, 0, 0)$ by representations of $N \times O(3, 1)$. The remaining question is how David's quantum states are related to the quantum states of a nearby observer.

The metric is no longer constant at first order, and thus a representation of $O(3, 1)$ is no longer sufficient. A natural and naive guess is to try representations of $GL(4)$. At each point in spacetime not too far from $(0, 0, 0, 0)$, we have a system of first order transformations $O_{x^\mu}(3, 1) = \{\Lambda : \Lambda^T g(x^\mu) \Lambda = g(x^\mu)\}$, and a $GL(4)$ -representation decomposes into irreducible representations of $O_{x^\mu}(3, 1)$, which is interpreted as the observation of the global quantum state as local particle physics phenomena (this vaguely invokes wavefunction collapse, but only vaguely). To work in more complicated 4-manifolds, one might need a global group larger than $GL(4)$, plus perhaps one of the many mathematical bundle structures for convenience. For the case of a country on Earth under Earth's gravity, my guess is that $GL(4)$ should be enough.

We note that when relating the many N groups of nearby observers, there may arise subtleties which need careful handling.

8 Large distance redshift

Suppose that a correct, experimentally verified gravity theory is already developed in the framework. Since the theory is covariant, we're free to choose whatever coordinates to use. If we use a large coordinate system (that is, the units are large, and the coordinate values are small), then matter, movement and energy are more concentrated; gravity is dominated by higher order graviton fields. If we use a small coordinate system (that is, the units are small, and the coordinate values are large), then matter, movement and energy are less concentrated; gravity is dominated by lower-order graviton fields. In other words, higher-order graviton fields are more relevant at higher energy, lower-order graviton fields are more relevant at lower energy.

One particular striking consequence of this is that, if we enlarge, for example, the LHC's facilities by 1 000 000 times (which is equivalent to reduce the units by 1 000 000 times), we would observe a physical situation with lower order graviton fields, a redshift in terms of graviton fields.

Now, assume further that gravitons somehow interact with other kinds of matter, specifically those which emit light in the visible spectrum, it would mean that there would be an observed redshift at very large distance.

At this point, although aware that the above argument is extremely speculative and not at all predictive, the author cannot help but feel a bit excited.

9 Conclusion

In this article, we have introduced a general symmetry group associated to each free falling observer, which, in spirit of the BMS group, extends the Lorentz symmetry group. The group turns out to be independent of the surrounding gravity. Some of its representations are constructed, which contain quite interesting structures: covariant translations, gravitons, k th order fields. Extension to accelerating observers seems doable.

The framework is to be developed so that it retrieves Einstein's theory of gravity, and to be verified experimentally. If the framework turns out to be correct, it may serve to construct higher order corrections to gravity theories, to physics of elementary particles and more generally physics of accelerating frames.

On the theoretical side, there might be possible works on classifying the local symmetry group's irreducible representations, describing the gravitons of n th order, describing gravi-instantons (N_∞ -representations), coupled states, scattering states, many-particle states which can lead to a quantum field theory, finer consideration for accelerating observers and global groups, second quantization of the tensorial fields,... The author's urge to publish stems, indeed, from the urge to see such developments to be realized.

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